

BACHELOR THESIS

Inhibition of Spoilage *Bacillus* spp. in Plant-Based Products

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Title: Inhibition of spoilage *Bacillus* spp. as in Plant-based Products

Subject description: Plant-based foods, particularly legumes, are in high demand due to their nutritional and environmental benefits. However, plant-based foods are exposed to microbiological spoilage, which leads to a decline in their quality and shelf life. *Bacillus* species are among the most common spoilage microorganisms. They are naturally found in soil, plants, and water, and can form hardy spores under unfavorable conditions. These spores are particularly problematic because they can withstand high heat, allowing them to survive heat processes. To improve the shelf life and quality of plant-based products, effective methods are being investigated to inhibit *Bacillus* species in these products. This project examines the method that involves the inhibition of *Bacillus* with lactic acid bacteria by for example investigating the concentration of organic acids and the benefits of decreasing pH to approximately 4.5.

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Abbreviations

BHI	Brain Heart Infusion
BB	Blue <i>Bacillus subtilis</i>
BG	Green <i>Bacillus licheniformis</i>
BII	<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i> (green) (Faba protein concentrate, Vestkorn, Denmark)
BI2	<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i> (red) (Faba protein concentrate, Vestkorn, Denmark)
Bs1	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> (blue) (isolated from dried faba beans, AM Nutrition, Norway)
Bs2	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> (yellow) (isolated from dried faba beans, AM Nutrition, Norway)
GM	GM17- <i>Lactococcus lactis</i>
GM17	Glucose M17
GMB	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> + <i>Lactococcus lactis</i>
GMG	<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i> + <i>Lactococcus lactis</i>
LAB	<i>Lactic Acid Bacteria</i>
M	MRS- <i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>
MB	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> + <i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>
MG	<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i> + <i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>
MRS	De Man, Rogosa, and Sharpe

Abstract

The increasing demand for plant-based foods highlights the need for improved preservation methods to combat microbiological spoilage, particularly by *Bacillus* spp. This study investigates the inhibition of *Bacillus subtilis* (*B. subtilis*) and *Bacillus licheniformis* (*B. licheniformis*) in plant-based products using hydrochloric acid (HCl), organic acids and lactic acid bacteria (LAB). Both strains, are known for their spore-forming and heat-resistant properties, which present significant challenges in maintaining product quality and shelf-life. HCl also showed inhibition of *Bacillus* growth at $\text{pH} \leq 3.5$, with no growth observed in Brain Heart Infusion (BHI) broth and limited recovery on BHI agar plates. The study further evaluated the inhibitory effects of lactic acid, acetic acid, and their synergistic combinations under varying pH conditions. Acetic acid (pK_a 4.76) demonstrated stronger antimicrobial effects at lower concentrations (42.05mM) and moderately acidic pH value (5.41), with 7.69mM undissociated acid resulting in complete growth inhibition in broth and minimal growth in agar plates. Lactic acid (pK_a 3.86) required lower pH (≤ 4.8) and higher concentrations to achieve similar inhibition. A synergistic combination of acetic and lactic acids further reduced the required concentrations for complete inhibition, with no bacterial growth observed at 42.05mM in both broth and agar media. LAB supernatants, particularly from *Limosilactobacillus fermentum* (*L. fermentum*) enhanced inhibition by reducing $\text{pH} < 4.5$ compared to *Lactococcus lactis* (*L. lactis*) where pH only achieve $\text{pH} > 5$. These findings demonstrate that combining organic acids and LAB-based strategies provides a highly effective method for mitigating *Bacillus*-related spoilage in plant-based foods. This natural preservation approach addresses the need for sustainable, minimally processed products while ensuring extended shelf life and improved quality.

Preface

This thesis, corresponding to 15 ECTS credits, and is mandatory for the bachelor's program (BSc) in Food Science and Nutrition with a specialization in Food Engineering at the University of Copenhagen. The project was conducted part-time over two blocks, between the 2nd of September 2024 to 17th of January 2025. Experimental work was completed at the Department of Food Science, the Faculty of Science, University of Copenhagen, Rolighedsvej 26, 1968 Frederiksberg.

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1 Introduction

The increasing demand for plant-based foods is driven by an increased focus on sustainability, health, and the need to reduce dependence on animal products. Faba beans (*Vicia faba*) are particularly promising as a local and sustainable protein source that can be grown in temperate climates. They contain high protein content with a good amino acid composition and can potentially replace soy in several food applications. (Bangar & Dhull, 2022)

Despite their advantages, plant-based products, including faba beans, face challenges with microbiological spoilage, which limits shelf life and product quality. A major reason for this is contamination with spore-forming bacteria, especially *Bacillus subtilis* (*B. subtilis*) and *Bacillus licheniformis* (*B. licheniformis*), which are naturally found in soil, plants, and water. These bacteria produce heat-resistant endospores that can survive conventional heat treatments such as pasteurization and thus remain present in the food (Angeles & Scheffers, 2020). The result is a quality and economic loss for food producers.

An effective method to inhibit the growth of these *Bacillus species* (*Bacillus* spp.) is the use of organic acids such as lactic acid and acetic acid (Reis et al., 2012). These acids lower the pH of the product and create an acidic environment that is unfavorable for the growth of bacteria and spores. At low pH values, the organic acids can enter bacterial cells in their undissociated form, after which they release protons inside the cell. This leads to an acidification of the cytoplasm, which inhibits the metabolism and growth of the bacteria (Rongxue Sun et al., 2021). Studies have shown that the combination of lactic acid and acetic acid can have a synergistic effect, improving the overall inhibition of *Bacillus* spp. at lower concentrations than when using a single acid alone (Reis et al., 2012).

The purpose of this task is to investigate how to inhibit the growth of *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis* in plant-based products such as faba beans as the ingredients. By reducing pH and analyzing the inhibitory effect of organic acids, we want to identify a method that can extend the shelf-life and improve the quality of these products.

2 Theory

2.1 Occurrence of *Bacillus*

Bacillus is a large and diverse genus of gram-positive, rod-shaped bacteria belonging to the family *Bacillaceae*. This genus is known for its ability to produce endospores that are highly resistant to adverse environmental conditions such as heat, chemicals and drought. This makes *Bacillus* a particularly important group in microbiology and food safety, as their spores often survive traditional preservation and heat treatment (Martin R Adams et al., 2016).

Species within the genus *Bacillus* have a wide ecological diversity and can be found in soil, water, plants, and as contaminants in food. These bacteria play an important role in nature's cycles, as they break down organic matter and recycle nutrients, which promotes plant growth and soil health. At the same time, certain species, such as *B. subtilis*, are used in fermentation and the production of enzymes and antibiotics. However, even *B. subtilis* can in some cases act as a contaminant and be associated with food spoilage and toxin production under adverse conditions, emphasizing that no *Bacillus* spp. can be considered completely harmless in the food context (Martin R Adams et al., 2016).

Bacillus spp. can grow under a wide range of temperatures, pH values, and other environmental conditions. For example, many *Bacillus* spp. can grow at low pH or high temperatures, making them some of the most robust microorganisms in food environments (Martin R Adams et al., 2016). Their spores can remain dormant for long periods of time and resume growth when conditions become favorable, creating challenges for food manufacturers, especially in plant-based products that often lack antimicrobial preservatives (Martin R Adams et al., 2016).

Within the *Bacillus* genus, some species are harmless or even beneficial under certain conditions, such as *B. subtilis*, which is used in probiotics and fermentation processes. However, it is important to note that even beneficial species such as *B. subtilis* can be problematic. Under uncontrolled conditions, *B. subtilis* can produce toxins or cause spoilage in plant-based products (Franceschini et al., 2020a). This contrasts with species such as *Bacillus cereus* (*B. cereus*), which are known to produce toxins that directly cause foodborne illness and are often found in contaminated foods such as rice and plant-based products. At the same time, *B. licheniformis* plays a dual role as both a contaminant and a beneficial microbe in industrial fermentation processes (Martin R Adams et al., 2016).

This understanding of the *Bacillus* genus highlights the importance of controlling growth and sporulation, as even species with commercial use can pose a risk under adverse conditions. Therefore, it is crucial to establish effective methods for monitoring and managing *Bacillus* in food production.

2.2 Structure and Physiology of *Bacillus subtilis*

The cell wall of *B. subtilis* is a complex and essential structure that provides the bacterium with shape, it protects it from the external environment and withstands osmotic pressure from within the cell. It is primarily composed of two main elements: peptidoglycan (PG) and anionic polymers such as teichoic acids and teichuronic acids. Peptidoglycan is an elastic, yet strong polymer made up of long glycan chains consisting of alternating N-acetylglucosamine (GlcNAc) and N-acetylmuramic acid (MurNAc), connected by β -1,4 linkages. These chains are cross-linked via flexible peptide bridges, giving the structure its strength (Angeles & Scheffers, 2020).

B. subtilis is a motile bacterium that moves using peritrichous flagella, which is small, thread-like structures evenly distributed around the cell. These flagella enable the bacterium to navigate through liquids and across solid surfaces to seek better nutrient conditions. It is facultatively anaerobic, meaning it can survive and grow both in the presence of oxygen and under oxygen-free conditions (Anupama Sapkota, 2022).

The bacterium produces endospores, which are resilient structures that allow it to survive extreme environmental conditions such as high heat, desiccation, and nutrient deprivation. This ability to form spores is a crucial survival strategy that ensures the bacterium's long-term presence in unfavorable environments (Anupama Sapkota, 2022). In soil environments, *B. subtilis* acts as a saprophyte, breaking down dead organic material. Its role in decomposition helps recycle nutrients and supports plant growth (Williams & Weir, 2024).

B. subtilis is also known for its ability to form biofilms on plant roots, playing a key role in agriculture and ecological systems. These biofilms protect plants from pathogens by creating a physical and chemical protective layer around the roots, preventing harmful microorganisms from colonizing the root surface. Additionally, biofilms enhance nutrient uptake by promoting the release and availability of essential nutrients in the root environment, thereby boosting plant growth and health (Ajijah et al., 2023).

2.2.1 Growth conditions of *Bacillus subtilis*

B. subtilis is classified as a mesophilic bacterium, favoring moderate temperature ranges for optimal growth. The bacterium grows within a temperature range of 13°C to 54°C, with optimal growth observed at approximately 46.9°C (Emilie Gauvry et al., 2020; Franceschini et al., 2020b). Its ability to grow within a pH range of 4.9 to 9.1, with an optimal pH of 6.8, further reflects its adaptability to varied environments. Additionally, water activity (a_w) is a crucial determinant of growth, with a minimum requirement of 0.929 and optimal growth achieved at a_w 0.996 (Franceschini et al., 2020b; Rosenquist & Hansen, 1998).

Furthermore *B. subtilis* produces endospores that are remarkably resistant to environmental stresses, including heat, desiccation, and chemical agents. The spore's multilayered structure, which includes a robust cortex and an impermeable coat, contributes to its resistance. The dehydrated core and the presence of small acid-soluble spore proteins (SASPs) protect DNA and other vital molecules from damage (Angeles & Scheffers, 2020).

Heat resistance is a defining characteristic of *B. subtilis* spores. The spores can withstand temperatures exceeding 100°C due to their low water content and high levels of calcium dipicolinate (Food Microbiology, 2016). They are also resistant to UV radiation and chemical disinfectants, making them challenging to eliminate in food production environments (Onyeaka & Nwabor, 2022).

2.2.2 Functionality and applications of *Bacillus subtilis*

B. subtilis functions in plants as a plant growth-promoting rhizobacterium (PGPR), supporting plant growth and stress management through multiple biological mechanisms. The microorganism is particularly effective under challenging conditions such as water and salt stress, where it enhances soil conditions and creates favorable growth environments for plants (Yang et al., 2015). One of the primary ways *B. subtilis* promotes plant growth is through hormone regulation. The bacterium can induce the secretion of auxins and cytokinin's in plants, which enhances the growth of leaves and other organs, while simultaneously inhibiting the production of the stress hormone abscisic acid. This creates optimal growth conditions and improves the plant's ability to absorb water and nutrients from the soil. By enhancing nitrogen uptake, *B. subtilis* further contributes to improved plant growth and development, especially under stress conditions such as water scarcity (Yang et al., 2015).

Additionally, *B. subtilis* plays a crucial role in improving soil structure and function. It releases organic acids that not only promote the formation of soil aggregates but also contribute to the release

of metal ions from mineral surfaces. This further enhances soil structure and increases its water retention capacity. These changes create stable and nutrient-rich soil that supports plant growth and makes it easier for plants to maintain growth, even in environments with limited water availability (Yang et al., 2015).

Furthermore, *B. subtilis* contributes to reducing soil salinity by releasing organic acids, which promote the conversion of inorganic phosphate into free phosphate and acidify the soil environment. These changes lower soil salinity, mitigating the negative effects of salt stress on plants (Yang et al., 2015). These mechanisms make *B. subtilis* an essential component in agricultural production, especially under stress conditions such as water and salt stress (Yang et al., 2015).

In addition to its role as a plant growth-promoting rhizobacterium, *B. subtilis* also has significant use in food fermentation and as a probiotic culture. *Bacillus subtilis* ssp. *natto* (*B. subtilis* spp. *natto*) is traditionally used in the production of natto, a fermented Japanese food made from soybeans. During fermentation, the bacterium produces enzymes such as natto kinase, which have health-promoting properties, including blood-thinning and fibrinolytic effects. In addition, the fermentation process promotes the release of bioactive peptides and increases the nutritional value of the product, making it more digestible and richer in essential nutrients such as vitamin K and antioxidants. This process not only improves taste and texture but also reduces antinutritional factors found in raw soybeans (Franceschini et al., 2020; Williams & Weir, 2024).

B. subtilis is also known as a robust probiotic organism used in dietary supplements and functional foods. Its ability to form spores makes it extremely stable during storage and in the acidic environment of the gastrointestinal tract. When the spores reach the intestine, they germinate and contribute to a healthy microflora. Probiotic strains of *B. subtilis* have been shown to strengthen the immune system, reduce inflammation and improve gut health. This makes the bacterium particularly valuable in the treatment and prevention of gastrointestinal disorders (Williams & Weir, 2024; Ajijah et al., 2023).

B. subtilis dual role as a fermentation culture and probiotic highlights its versatility and utility in both traditional and modern food technologies. At the same time, this underlines the importance of precise and controlled fermentation conditions to maximize its beneficial properties and minimize the risk of unwanted growth of pathogenic or toxin-producing strains.

2.3 Structure and use of *Bacillus licheniformis*

Like *B. subtilis*, *B. licheniformis* is a spore-forming, Gram-positive bacterium with broad applications in biotechnology. It thrives in soil and marine environments, demonstrating resilience to extreme conditions such as high salinity and temperature. *B. licheniformis* produces thermostable enzymes like α -amylases, which are widely used in the food industry, particularly in baking and dairy processes (He et al., 2023).

Despite its industrial significance, *B. licheniformis* can also act as a contaminant, posing risks in food production. Its spores can survive pasteurization, making effective control measures crucial (Franceschini et al., 2020b).

The cell wall of *B. licheniformis* is made up of a thick peptidoglycan layer containing N-acetylglucosamine, N-acetylmuramic acid, and amino acids like glutamic acid, diaminopimelic acid, and alanine. These components give the cell wall strength and help the bacterium resist osmotic stress and other external pressures. Studies show that the cell wall is well-structured, with specific amino acid sequences that add to its stability (Hughes, 1968). For example, both D- and L-alanine are found in the mucopeptide structure, playing a key role in keeping the cell wall strong and functional (Hughes, 1968).

The bacterium is facultatively anaerobic. This flexibility allows the bacterium to thrive in a wide range of environments, from soil to food products. It can break down various substrates, including sugars and proteins, making it useful in industrial processes like enzyme production (Mareeswaran Jeyaraman & Evgeni Eltzov, 2024).

It naturally lives in soil, marine environments, and on plants. Soil is an especially important habitat, where the bacterium breaks down organic materials and helps recycle nutrients, supporting the soil ecosystem (He et al., 2023). In marine areas, it can survive tough conditions like high salt concentrations and changing temperatures, making it a key player in these environments.

B. licheniformis holds significant value in biotechnology and industry due to its ability to produce enzymes that are highly effective in various applications. For instance, thermostable α -amylases from *B. licheniformis* are utilized in the baking industry to reduce dough viscosity and extend the freshness of bread. Similarly, β -galactosidase from this bacterium is employed in dairy products to break down

lactose, enhancing sweetness and solubility. Its resilience to high temperatures makes it an excellent source of enzymes suitable for the demanding conditions of food processing (He et al., 2023).

Table 1: Summary of Key Differences and Similarity Between *Bacillus subtilis* and *Bacillus licheniformis*

Parameter	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i>
Taxonomy	Class: <i>Bacilli</i> Family: <i>Bacillaceae</i>	Class: <i>Bacilli</i> Family <i>Bacillaceae</i>
Shape and Morphology	Gram-positive, rod-shaped, spore-forming	Gram-positive, rod-shaped, spore-forming
Environmental adaption	Tolerates high heat and adverse conditions, prefers soil and plant roots as its habitat.	It thrives in soil and marine environments, can survive high salinity and extreme conditions.
Health significance	Used as a probiotic and in fermented foods like natto. Contributes to gut health and strengthens the immune system.	Can produce toxins under unfavorable conditions. Known for surviving in food and causing spoilage
Enzyme production	Produces proteases, amylases, and cellulases. Commonly used in agriculture and research.	Produces thermostable enzymes like alpha-amylase and proteases. Used in the bakery and detergent industries.
Food applications	Fermentation culture for natto and as a probiotic in supplements.	Less used in fermentation but significant for industrial enzyme production.
pH and temperature optimal growth	4.9-9.1 (optimal pH: 6.8) 13-54°C (optimal: 46.9°C)	4.6-6.0 (optimal pH: ~5.5) 30-50°C (optimal: ~37-40°C)
Risk factors	Can produce toxins under adverse conditions but is generally safe in controlled processes	Produces biofilms and toxins in food under unfavorable conditions. Survives pasteurization.

B. subtilis and *B. licheniformis* are both Gram-positive, spore-forming bacteria, but they exhibit distinct applications and risks. *B. subtilis* is widely recognized for its use as a probiotic and fermentation agent in foods like natto, as well as its enzyme production capabilities. In contrast, *B. licheniformis* is highly valued for its thermostable enzymes in industrial processes, though it poses a greater spoilage risk due to biofilm formation and potential toxin production.

2.4 *Bacillus* as a contaminant in plant-based foods

Plant-based products, including soya and faba beans, have gained increasing popularity as sustainable alternatives to animal-based foods. These products are distinguished by their high nutritional value and applicability in various culinary applications. Soybeans (*Glycine max*) are recognized for their balanced amino acid profile and are widely used in products such as tofu, soy beverages and plant-based meat substitutes. Furthermore, they are associated with potential health benefits, including reduced risk of cardiovascular disease and certain types of cancer (Qin et al., 2022).

Faba beans are another important crop that provides high quality protein and essential amino acids. This bean also contributes to sustainable agricultural practices through fixation, reducing the need for chemical fertilizers and improving soil health (Bangar & Dhull, 2022). However, these products can be exposed to microbiological contamination during production and storage, which can degrade their quality and pose a risk to consumer safety.

2.4.1 *Bacillus* in plant-based products

Bacillus spp. is everywhere. They are often found in soil and can easily contaminate plant-based products. *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis* are the most prominent species that cause spoilage and toxin production. These species form spores that are highly resistant to heat treatment and chemical disinfectants, making them challenging to control (Rosenkvist & Hansen, 1995); (Fernandes & Jobby, 2022).

One study has shown that *B. cereus* occurs in up to 40% of plant-based products (Fernandes & Jobby, 2022). In comparison, the prevalence of *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis* is typically lower, but they still pose a significant risk in foods with high moisture content. While there are no established acceptable risk levels for *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis*, concentrations above 10^5 cfu/g are considered potentially problematic in foods as they can lead to spoilage and mild foodborne illness (Rosenkvist & Hansen, 1995). This highlights the need for close monitoring and control of their growth.

The above-mentioned *Bacillus* spp. can multiply rapidly under favorable conditions and reach concentrations of up to 10^7 cfu/g in products such as bread within two days of baking if storage conditions are not adequately controlled (Rosenkvist & Hansen, 1995). This occurrence indicates the need for effective strategies to inhibit *Bacillus* growth in plant-based products.

2.4.2 Toxin production

B. subtilis and *B. licheniformis* are two-faced microorganisms in the food industry. They can cause significant spoilage but are also used as fermenters in controlled processes. These processes improve the texture, taste and nutritional value of the product. (Fernandes & Jobby, 2022; Franceschini et al., 2020b). For example, *B. subtilis* is used in the production of natto, a traditional Japanese fermented soy dish. However, it is crucial to ensure strictly controlled fermentation conditions to avoid unintended growth of toxin-producing strains (Qin et al., 2022). Another study showed that the addition of 15% sourdough, fermented with *Lactobacillus sanfrancisco*, could significantly reduce *Bacillus* growth in wheat bread. This was achieved by lowering the pH of the bread to below 4.8, which is below the critical level for spore growth (Rosenkvist & Hansen, 1998).

2.4.3 Preventing *Bacillus* contamination

Effective prevention of *Bacillus* contamination requires several different strategies. A combination of low pH and reduced water activity has been documented to be effective in inhibiting *Bacillus*

growth. For example, a combination of pH 5.1 and a water activity of 0.92 has been shown to prevent spore germination in several *Bacillus* spp. (Franceschini et al., 2020b).

The use of natural antimicrobial agents, such as bacteriocins from Lactic acid bacteria (LAB), has also shown promise. These compounds can effectively inhibit *Bacillus* spp. without compromising the sensory quality of the product (Fernandes & Jobby, 2022). Furthermore, the addition of sourdough, fermented with *Lactobacillus* spp., can be a natural way to reduce *Bacillus* growth by utilizing organic acids and low pH (Rosenquist & Hansen, 1998). Innovative technologies such as aseptic packaging and ultraviolet radiation can further minimize the risk of contamination. These technologies have been shown to be effective in reducing the number of *Bacillus* spores in processed plant-based products (Heyndrickx & Scheldeman, 2008).

2.5 Inhibition of *Bacillus* spp.

2.5.1 Effects of Hydrochloric acid on Bacterial survival and Adaption

Inorganic acids such as Hydrochloric acid (HCl), are strong acids that completely dissociate in aqueous solutions. This means that they increase the concentration of free protons (H⁺) in the solution, thereby lowering the pH. Despite their ability to create external acid stress, inorganic acids have a limited ability to penetrate bacterial cells (Wilks et al., 2009).

When HCl lowers the pH of the surrounding environment, bacteria respond primarily by attempting to maintain their intracellular pH through various survival mechanisms. For example, *B. subtilis* has been shown to increase the production of proton-pumping enzymes and decarboxylases, which help remove excess protons from the cell interior (Wilks et al., 2009). This adaption reduces acid stress and allows continued metabolic activity. However, HCl primarily creates an external stress environment in which bacterial growth is inhibited to a lesser extent than by organic acids. Its limited intracellular effect is due to its inability to cross bacterial cell membranes to any significant extent.

2.5.2 Acetic acid: Mechanisms of Bacterial Inhibition and Survival

Acetic acid is a widely recognized organic acid with a strong inhibitory effect on bacterial growth, surpassing many inorganic acids (Rongxue Sun et al., 2021). One key factor is its ability to cross bacterial cell membranes in its undissociated form. Once inside the bacterial cell, acetic acid dissociates into protons and anions, leading to cascade of effects that disrupt bacterial metabolism intracellular pH balance and creating a hostile environment for cellular metabolism (Rongxue Sun et al., 2021).

The dissociation of acetic acid within the cytoplasm lowers intracellular pH, impairing enzymatic activity and other vital cellular processes. Simultaneously, anions accumulate, cause osmotic stress and potentially exerting direct toxicity on the bacterial cell. In response, bacteria like *B. subtilis* activate energy-intensive defense mechanisms, such as proton pumps to expel excess protons and stabilize intracellular pH. However, this process depletes the cell's energy reserves, weakening its overall survival capacity (Yang et al., 2015).

Acetic acid's inhibitory potency is closely tied to its chemical properties, particularly its lower molecular weight and higher proportion of undissociated molecules at equivalent pH values compared to other organic acids. These characteristics make it especially effective in acidic environments, where it can penetrate bacterial membranes efficiently and disrupts cellular processes more effectively than lactic acid (Rongxue Sun et al., 2021).

2.5.3 Lactic acid: Impact on Bacterial Cells and Adaptive Responses

Lactic acid is another organic acid and a weak acid, meaning that it does not completely dissociate in solution. In a low pH environment, a significant proportion of lactic acid remains in its undissociated form, allowing the acid to penetrate bacterial cell membranes. When lactic acid diffuses into the cell, it dissociates in the neutral intracellular environment, releasing protons (H^+). This process lowers the intracellular pH and creates an acid stress that disrupts essential enzymatic functions and metabolic processes. Bacteria such as *B. subtilis* respond to this by upregulating genes involved in acid tolerance, such as *cadA* and *czcDO*, which help transport toxic metals out of the cell and minimize cell damage (Wilks et al., 2009). While lactic acid is less effective compared to acetic acid at equivalent concentrations, it remains a critical organic acid in food preservation.

2.5.4 Synergistic effects of acetic acid and lactic acid

Recent studies have further demonstrated the antifungal potential of lactic acid, particularly against strains of *Aspergillus flavus*, a significant producer of foodborne toxins (Reis et al., 2012). Interestingly, acetic acid shows a more consistent minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) across different strains, while the MIC of lactic acid varies and often requires higher concentrations to achieve comparable effects. When used in combination, lactic acid and acetic acid exhibit a synergistic effect. This means that the concentration of each acid required to inhibit fungal growth is significantly reduced compared to their individual use. This synergistic effect highlights the potential of using organic acid mixtures to improve antimicrobial efficacy in fermentation processes where microbial growth control is crucial (Reis et al., 2012).

2.5.5 The Impact of Organic Acids on *Bacillus subtilis* and *Bacillus licheniformis*

Acetic acid and lactic acid play a significant role in inhibiting the growth of spore-forming bacteria like *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis*. Their inhibitory effect arises from a combination of pH reduction and specific mechanisms that disrupt the physiological functions of bacterial cells (Rongxue Sun et al., 2021). Low pH significantly inhibits the growth of *B. licheniformis*, which typically activates the arginine deiminase (ADI) pathway to generate ammonia and raise the internal pH. However, this mechanism is significantly impaired in the presence of acetic acid, which blocks arginine metabolism and reduces sugar consumption. At concentrations of 10.20 mM protonated acetic acid (equivalent to a total acetic acid concentration of 25-50 mM), growth of *B. licheniformis* can be completely inhibited at pH 4.6 (Yang et al., 2015).

Acetic acid and lactic acid have also demonstrated a synergistic effect when used together. The simultaneous use of acetic acid and lactic acid enhances the inhibition of *B. subtilis*, even at concentrations that would be insufficient individually. This synergistic effect is particularly evident at pH values below 5.0, where the combined presence of both acids significantly enhances their inhibitory impact (Rongxue Sun et al., 2021). Together, acetic acid and lactic acid emerge as highly effective strategies for limiting the growth of *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis* under acidic conditions.

Figure 1: The figure illustrates the distinct and combined mechanisms of action of hydrochloric acid (HCl), acetic acid, and lactic acid on Gram-positive *Bacillus* spp. cells. Hydrochloric acid creates external acid stress on the cell wall without penetrating the membrane, resulting in limited intracellular disruption. In contrast, acetic acid penetrates the bacterial membrane in its undissociated form and dissociates into protons (H⁺) and anions inside the cell, lowering intracellular pH and disrupting vital metabolic processes. Similarly, lactic acid enters the cell, lowering intracellular pH and inhibiting enzymatic activity, while simultaneously increasing the energy demand due to the activation of proton pumps. The synergistic effect of acetic and lactic acid further enhances bacterial inhibition by amplifying pH disruption, metabolic interference, and energy demand, leading to a more potent antibacterial effect. This figure highlights the differences and interactions between acids in inhibiting Gram-positive bacteria effectively.

2.6 Lactic acid bacteria

2.6.1 Physiology of *Lactococcus lactis*: Metabolism and Environmental Adaptations

Lactococcus lactis (*L. lactis*) is a Gram-positive, non-motile, and facultatively anaerobic bacterium belonging to the family *Streptococcaceae*. It efficiently ferments hexose carbohydrates via the Embden-Meyerhof-Parnas (EMP) pathway, producing lactic acid as the primary metabolic end-product. This acidification lowers the environmental pH, inhibiting the growth of competing microorganisms and enhancing its application in food preservation (Wang et al., 2021). As a mesophilic organism, *L. lactis* thrives at an optimal growth temperature of approximately 30°C, making it ideal for its role in the production of fermented foods such as cheese and yogurt (Martin R Adams et al., 2016).

2.6.2 Metabolism and Lactic acid Production of *Lactococcus lactis*

L. lactis primarily metabolizes glucose through glycolysis, where the glucose is converted into pyruvate, subsequently reduced to lactate-by-lactate dehydrogenase (LDH). This process regenerates NAD⁺, ensuring the continuation of glycolysis and creating a rapid acidification of the environment, which is critical in inhibiting pathogenic microorganisms (Wang et al., 2021).

Under glucose-limited environments, *L. lactis* exhibits metabolic flexibility by employing alternative pathways, such as the pentose phosphate pathway (PPP), to metabolize pentose sugars and generate NADPH for biosynthesis and oxidative stress resistance (Suo et al., 2021). In oxygen-rich conditions, it undergoes mixed-acid fermentation, producing acetate, ethanol, and formate alongside lactic acid, enhancing ATP-yield and survival (Suo et al., 2021). Additionally, *L. lactis* metabolize citrate, converting it into pyruvate via citratase. Pyruvate is then transformed into acetoin and diacetyl, secondary metabolites that contribute to the buttery flavor and aroma characteristic of fermented products (Wang et al., 2021).

2.6.3 Nisin and bacteriocins

L. lactis is known for its ability to produce bacteriocins, including nisin, one of the most widely studied and applied lantibiotics. Nisin, classified as a Class I bacteriocin, is composed of unusual amino acids such as lanthionine and methyllanthionine, which contribute to its heat stability and antimicrobial efficacy. Its primary mode of action involves binding to lipid II, a precursor in bacterial cell wall synthesis, leading to pore formation, ion leakage, and cell death. This mechanism is particularly effective against Gram-positive bacteria, including *Clostridium botulinum* (*C. botulinum*), *B. subtilis*, and *Listeria monocytogenes* (*L. monocytogenes*) (S. Mills et al., 2011).

Beyond nisin, *L. lactis* can produce other bacteriocins such as lacticin 3147 and lacticin 481, both of which exhibit broad-spectrum activity against foodborne pathogens and spoilage organisms. Lacticin 3147 has been employed in the production of dairy products like buttermilk, where its application helps control spoilage and enhance microbial safety (Wang et al., 2021).

Recent advancements emphasize the synergistic use of nisin with other natural antimicrobials to enhance its efficacy. For example, combining nisin with organic acids such as acetic and lactic acids have demonstrated enhanced membrane disruption capabilities, effectively reducing pathogen proliferation in dairy matrices. Additionally, the incorporation of nisin with essential oils for nanoparticles has been shown to broaden its antimicrobial spectrum, making it more effective against resistant strains and Gram-negative bacteria (Yu et al., 2023).

Nisin's stability and efficacy under various conditions, including high temperatures and low pH, make it a versatile preservative for a wide range of food products. As an approved food additive (E234), it is extensively used in dairy, meat, and canned foods to ensure microbial safety while reducing the reliance on synthetic preservatives (Wang et al., 2021).

2.6.4 Technological Properties and Applications of *Lactococcus lactis*

L. lactis is widely utilized as a starter culture in the dairy and fermentation industries. Its ability to produce lactic acid and bacteriocins enhances food safety and extends the shelf life of products without altering sensory attributes such as taste and texture (Reis et al., 2012).

Studies have shown that the addition of nisin to products like milk and cheese significantly improves food safety by inhibiting pathogenic microorganisms. This is particularly advantageous under high-temperature conditions, where nisin's stability ensures consistent antimicrobial efficacy. Furthermore, as a natural bio preservative, *L. lactis* and its metabolites are instrumental in reducing reliance on synthetic preservatives. Approved as a food additive (E234), nisin is widely employed to control spore formation in dairy products and heat-treated foods. Additionally, secondary metabolites such as diacetyl contribute to the aroma and flavor of fermented products, enhancing their market appeal (S. Mills et al., 2011).

2.6.5 Antimicrobial Mechanisms of *Lactococcus lactis*

The antimicrobial properties of *L. lactis* arise from its dual action of environmental acidification and bacteriocin production. This combination creates conditions unfavorable for pathogens like *C. botulinum* and *B. cereus*, cementing its role as a natural bio preservative (Wang et al., 2021).

2.6.6 Metabolic and Antimicrobial Properties of *Limosilactobacillus fermentum*

Limosilactobacillus fermentum (*L. fermentum*, formerly *Lactobacillus fermentum*) is a Gram-positive bacterium classified within the genus *Limosilactobacillus*. As a facultative heterofermentative species, it can metabolize hexoses to produce various metabolites depending on environmental conditions and substrate availability. These metabolites include lactic acid, carbon dioxide (CO₂), ethanol, and acetic acid, with lactic acid typically being the primary active metabolite (Reis et al., 2012).

Under glucose-rich conditions, *L. fermentum* predominantly utilizes the glycolytic pathway. In this process, glucose is broken down into pyruvate, which is subsequently converted into lactic acid by lactate dehydrogenase. This pathway, known as homolactic fermentation, is highly efficient and enables rapid acidification, which is essential for inhibiting spoilage microorganisms (Wang et al., 2021).

When glucose is limited or pentoses are present, *L. fermentum* switches to the phosphoketolase pathway, a heterolactic fermentation process. This pathway allows to produce a mixture of lactic acid, acetic acid, ethanol, and CO₂. Acetic acid plays a particularly important role in its antimicrobial activity by disrupting microbial membranes. In its non-dissociated form, acetic acid permeates microbial cell membranes and dissociates within the cytoplasm, causing pH homeostasis disruption and interference with cellular processes (Wang et al., 2021).

Beyond its organic acid production, *L. fermentum* synthesizes bacteriocins, which are ribosomal synthesized antimicrobial peptides capable of inhibiting the growth of pathogenic and spoilage microorganisms. These bacteriocins typically disrupt the cell membranes of target organisms, causing ion leakage and eventual cell lysis. Examples include Fermencin SA715, which is stable across a wide range of pH levels and temperatures; Fermencin SD11, which is particularly effective against *L. monocytogenes*; and Bacteriocin L23, which demonstrates strong activity against Gram-positive bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) and *B. cereus* (Fernandes & Jobby, 2022).

The bacteriocins produced by *L. fermentum* are small, heat-stable, and resistant to pH fluctuations, making them highly suitable for food preservation. These properties, combined with their broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity, ensure their effectiveness against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, although their action is generally more potent against Gram-positive bacteria. The combination of metabolic flexibility and antimicrobial properties underscores the versatility of *L. fermentum* in food fermentation. By modulating its metabolic pathways and producing both organic acids and bacteriocins, it ensures adaptability to diverse fermentation conditions and enhances the safety and quality of fermented foods (Owusu-Kwarteng et al., 2015).

2.6.7 Technological properties of *Limosilactobacillus fermentum*

In food fermentation, *L. fermentum* serves as an essential natural starter culture due to its ability to rapidly acidify its environment through lactic acid production. This acidification creates unfavorable conditions for undesirable microorganisms, reducing fermentation time and minimizing contamination risks. Studies have shown that *L. fermentum* can lower the pH to below 4.5 within hours, highlighting its efficiency as a rapid acidifier (Owusu-Kwarteng et al., 2015).

Additionally, *L. fermentum* produces extracellular polysaccharides (EPS), which enhance the texture, viscosity, and stability of fermented foods. EPS play a dual role by improving sensory qualities and providing protection for the bacteria under challenging environmental conditions, such as low pH or high salt concentrations. In industrial applications, the antimicrobial properties of *L. fermentum* are particularly valuable. The synergistic effect of lactic and acetic acids reduces the concentrations required for effective microbial inhibition. This synergy broadens the spectrum of inhibited microorganisms, making it an effective strategy for controlling spoilage and pathogenic bacteria. Studies have demonstrated that this combination is especially effective in acidic environments, where the non-dissociated forms of both acids predominate (Reis et al., 2012).

Moreover, the production of bacteriocins further enhances *L. fermentum*'s utility in food preservation. These peptides contribute to the inhibition of pathogens, such as *L. monocytogenes*, while maintaining stability under a wide range of pH values and temperatures. Bacteriocins are particularly useful in high-risk foods, where contamination from Gram-positive bacteria is a concern.

The production of EPS, along with its acidification capabilities and antimicrobial metabolites, positions *L. fermentum* as a versatile and indispensable microorganism in both traditional and modern

food fermentation systems. Its ability to adapt to various substrates and environmental conditions makes it highly valuable for industrial-scale applications.

A deeper understanding of the differences between *L. lactis* and *L. fermentum* is essential for assessing their use in food fermentation and their effectiveness in inhibiting spore-forming bacteria such as *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis*. While *L. lactis* is particularly effective through its nisin production and pH lowering, *L. fermentum* combines the production of both lactic and acetic acids for a broader antimicrobial effect. These differences are essential for their use in various fermentation processes, as illustrated in the table below (Reis et al., 2012).

Table 2: Overview of the main differences between *Lactococcus lactis* and *Limosilactobacillus fermentum*

Parameter	<i>Lactococcus lactis</i>	<i>Limosilactobacillus fermentum</i>
Fermentation method	Homofermentive	Heterofermentive
Primary metabolites	Lactic acid, nisin	Lactic acid, acetic acid, ethanol
Applications	Dairy products (cheese, butter)	Vegetable fermented foods
Antimicrobial mechanisms	Nisin production, pH lowering	PH-lowering, acetic acid, bacteriocins
Synergies	Stabile in high temperature	Synergy with other acids such as acetic acid

L. lactis produces nisin, a bacteriostatic peptide that effectively inhibits the growth of gram-positive bacteria such as *Bacillus* spp. by interfering with their cell wall synthesis. This direct interaction makes it particularly effective in dairy products. On the other hand, it exerts a broader inhibitory effect through the production of both lactic acid and acetic acid. This combination lowers the pH and creates an environment that synergistically inhibits *Bacillus* spp. while negatively affecting competing bacteria. Its ability to produce bacteriocins that destabilize the cell membrane of other microorganisms further enhances its antimicrobial effect.

3 Materials and Methods

3.1 Bacterial strains

The experiments were conducted using *B. subtilis* strains (Bs1 (blue) and Bs2 (yellow)), isolated from dried faba beans provided by AM Nutrition, Norway, and *B. licheniformis* strains (B11 (green) and B12 (red)), obtained from faba protein concentrate from Vestkorn, Denmark as target microorganisms. These strains were selected for their potential to spoil plant-based food. The LAB used for inhibition experiments included *L. lactis* and *L. fermentum*, obtained from the Department of Food Science, University of Copenhagen's culture collection.

3.2 Cultivation of *Bacillus* strains and Lactic acid bacteria

Bacillus spp. was cultivated in Brain Heart Infusion (BHI) broth at 30°C. The BHI broth (M210-500G) used in these experiments was sourced from HIMEDIA. Cultures were prepared by inoculating

10 mL of sterile (autoclaved in 121°C for 2 hours) BHI broth with 0.1 mL of an overnight bacterial culture and incubating for 24 hours. Growth was assessed in both liquid BHI broth and solid BHI agar media. The agar medium was prepared by adding 10 g of agar to 500 mL of BHI broth. The solution was then sterilized by autoclaving at 121 °C for 2 hours. After sterilization, the agar was poured into sterile petri dishes and allowed to solidify before use.

L. lactis was cultivated in GM17 broth (Glucose M17) prepared by adding 10 mL of 50% (D (+) - Glucose monohydrate (Millipore) to M17 (M1029-500G) from HIMEDIA). Similarly, *L. fermentum* was cultivated in *Lactobacillus* MRS-broth (GM369-500G) from HIMEDIA at 30°C under static conditions. Both LAB cultures were incubated at 30°C under static conditions for 20-24 hours.

3.3 Growth of Various pH values and concentration of organic acids

Experiments were conducted using pH-adjusted BHI broth at specific pH values (2.5, 3.0, 3.5, 4.0, 4.5, 5.0, 5.5, and 6.0) using HCl and NaOH. Each pH-adjusted broth was distributed into sterile test tubes (10 mL per tube), inoculated with 0.1 mL of bacterial culture, and incubated at 30°C for 20-24 hours. Growth was assessed visually and confirmed quantitatively through plating on BHI agar.

The inhibitory effects of lactic acid and acetic acid were evaluated by adding them to the growth media at final concentrations of 20.6 mM, 42.05 mM, 63.5 mM, 84.95 mM, and 106.4 mM. The acids were added after sterilization and immediately before inoculation. Control samples without added acids were included in all experiments.

The combination of acetic acid and lactic acid was also tested to assess their synergistic effects. Acid solutions were prepared by adding calculated volumes of lactic acid and acetic acid to BHI-broth, with pH adjustments as necessary. Each solution was sterilized and inoculated as described in section 3.2. Although for the combined solutions, equal volumes (5 mL each) of lactic acid and acetic acid stock solutions were mixed to achieve the final concentrations. For example, 5 mL of 20.6 mM lactic acid solution and 5 mL of 20.6 mM acetic acid solution were combined to create a total volume of 10 mL, resulting in a final concentration of 20.6 mM for each acid in the mixture. This approach was applied for all tested concentrations (42.05 mM, 63.5 mM, 84.95 mM, and 106.4 mM). The calculations for the achieved concentrations are found in Appendix 1.

3.4 Effect of Lactic Acid Bacteria Supernatants

Supernatants from *L. lactis* and *L. fermentum* cultures were prepared by centrifuging overnight cultures at 4225x g for 10 minutes. The supernatants were filtered through a 0.22 µm filter to ensure sterility. These supernatants were added to *Bacillus* cultures at a ratio of 50:50 (50% supernatant: 50% *Bacillus* media), 60:40 (60% Supernatant: 40% *Bacillus* media) and 70:30 (70%Supernatant: 30% *Bacillus* media) and 25:25:50 (25% supernatant: 25% *Bacillus* media: 50% Milli-Q water). The mixtures were incubated at 30°C, and bacterial growth was quantified by optical density (OD600), colony-forming unit (CFU) counts (however the results of CFU are not included as some of them plates were too difficult to count (appendix 4)), and pH measurements.

3.5 Quantification of Organic Acids

Organic acid (acetic acid and lactic acid) concentrations were measured using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). Samples were filtered through 0.22 µm filters, and 20 µL of each sample was injected into the HPLC system. The system used was an Agilent Technologies 1260 Infinity II, equipped with a G1367E autosampler capable of precise sample handling and a UV detector set at 210 nm. The column used was a reverse-phase C18 column, and the mobile phase consisted of 0.1% phosphoric acid at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. Retention times were compared to those of known standard for lactic acid and acetic acids.

3.6 Optical Growth Quantification

Optical density (OD) measurements at 600 nm (OD600) were performed to monitor bacterial growth over time. The measurements were conducted using a GENESYS 180 spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific) equipped with software version 3.3.0.6. To ensure accuracy, sterile BHI broth was used as a blank reference for all readings. Samples were measured in 1 mL cuvettes, ensuring consistent optical path lengths and minimizing light scattering artifacts.

3.7 pH Regulation

The pH of all solutions was carefully adjusted and consistently monitored using a calibrated pH meters (MeterLab PHM250 Ion Analyzer and Mettler Toledo FiveEasy pH/mV) to ensure accuracy and reliability throughout the experiments. The calibration of both pH meters was conducted prior to measurements using certified standard buffer solutions at pH 4.01 and 7.00. Adjustments to the pH

were precisely achieved by the gradual addition of 0.1 M HCl or 0.1 M NaOH, depending on the required pH level.

3.8 Data Analysis and Statistics

Data analysis was conducted using R version 4.1.2 (R Core Team) and Microsoft Excel. A paired t-test was performed in R to evaluate the statistical significance of changes in optical density (OD) before and after incubation, with significance accepted at $p < 0.05$. Visualizations, including pH and OD plots, calculations of undissociated acid concentrations, and standard deviations for pH measurements across mixture ratios were completed in R. Standard curves for measurements were made in Excel, while R was used to visualize lactic acid and acetic acid concentrations.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Antimicrobial effect of inorganic acid - Hydrochloric acid

The antimicrobial properties of HCl were evaluated by monitoring the growth of *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis* across a pH gradient ranging from 2.5 to 6.0. Table 3 summarizes the growth responses of bacterial strains, classified as strong (+++), moderate (++), weak (+), very weak growth (+/-) or no growth (-) (Appendix 2). The data were obtained from experiments conducted in both BHI broth and agar media.

Table 3: Growth response of *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis* Across a pH Gradient

pH	<i>B. subtilis</i>				<i>B. licheniformis</i>			
	Bs1 Broth	Bs1 Agar	Bs2 Broth	Bs2 Agar	B11 Broth	B11 Agar	B12 Broth	B12 Agar
6.0	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++
5.5	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++
5.0	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	++
4.5	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
4.0	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	+
3.5	-	+/-	-	+/-	-	+/-	-	+/-
3.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

The table shows the growth response of *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis*, across pH gradient, when adjusted with the inorganic acid HCL. Growth was assessed visually based on the turbidity of the growth medium and colony formation in agar plates, as shown in figure 1. Blue: *B. subtilis*, Yellow: *B. subtilis*, Green: *B. licheniformis*, Red: *B. licheniformis*

The data in Table 3 demonstrate a clear relationship between pH and bacterial growth. At higher pH values (6.0-5.0), both *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis* exhibited strong to moderate growth (+++/++) in both broth and agar, indicating that HCl had limited inhibitory effects under neutral to slightly acidic conditions. As the pH decreased to 4.0, growth was significantly reduced, weak growth (+)

observed on agar and no detectable growth (-) in broth. At pH 3.5, no growth was observed for either *B. subtilis* or *B. licheniformis* in broth and very weak growth (+/-) in agar media. These findings highlight the increased inhibitory effect of HCl at lower pH values.

4.2 Antimicrobial effects of Organic Acids

4.2.1 Inhibitory Effect of Lactic Acid

Table 4 summarizes the growth inhibition of *B. subtilis* (Bs1 and Bs2) and *B. licheniformis* (B11 and B12) under different concentrations of lactic acid, with their corresponding pH values. Growth was recorded for both BHI broth and BHI agar media.

Table 4: Growth inhibition of *Bacillus* Strains at different concentrations of Lactic Acid

pH	Concentration	<i>B. subtilis</i>				<i>B. licheniformis</i>			
		Bs1 Broth	Bs1 Agar	Bs2 Broth	Bs2 Agar	B11 Broth	B11 Agar	B12 Broth	B12 Agar
6.78	20.6 mM	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++
5.65	42.05mM	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
4.80	63.5 mM	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4.36	84.95 mM	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4.06	106 mM	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

This table demonstrates the growth or inhibition of *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis* under varying concentrations of lactic acid. Strong growth is indicated by a "+++" symbol, while weak growth is "+" and no growth is represented by a "-" symbol. (Appendix 2) Color codes represent the strains: Blue for *B. subtilis* (Bs1), Yellow for *B. subtilis* (Bs2), Green for *B. licheniformis* (B11), and Red for *B. licheniformis* (B12).

As shown in Table 4, lactic acid exhibited minimal inhibitory effects compared to acetic acid.

At the lowest concentration 20.6mM and the corresponding pH 6.78, strong growth (+++) with no inhibition was observed in either broth or agar. However, at concentrations ≥ 63.5 mM and $\text{pH} \leq 4.80$, no growth (-) was observed across all strains in either broth or agar media, indicating complete inhibition.

4.2.2 Inhibitory Effect of Acetic Acid

Table 5 presents the growth inhibition of *B. subtilis* (Bs1 and Bs2) and *B. licheniformis* (B11 and B12) under different concentrations of acetic acid and corresponding pH values. Growth responses were evaluated in both BHI broth and agar media.

Table 5 5: Growth inhibition of *Bacillus* Strains at different concentrations of Acetic Acid

pH	Concentration	<i>B. subtilis</i>				<i>B. licheniformis</i>			
		Bs1 Broth	Bs1 Agar	Bs2 Broth	Bs2 Agar	B11 Broth	B11 Agar	B12 Broth	B12 Agar
6.56	20.6 mM	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++
5.41	42.05mM	-	-/+	-	-/+	-	-/+	-	-/+
4.85	63.5 mM	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4.67	84.95 mM	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4.51	106 mM	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

The table demonstrates the growth inhibition of *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis* at varying concentrations of acetic acid and corresponding pH levels in both BHI broth and BHI agar. Growth is indicated by a "+" symbol, very weak growth by a "+/-" symbol, while no growth is represented by a "-" symbol. (Appendix 2)

As shown in Table 5, at the lowest concentration of 20.6 mM and a corresponding pH of 6.56, strong growth (+++) was observed for all strains in both broth and agar media. At a concentration of 42.05 mM (pH 5.41), bacterial growth was inhibited in broth for all strains, while only very weak growth (+/-) was observed on agar for some strains. At concentrations ≥ 84.95 mM (pH ≤ 4.67), no growth (-) was detected across any strains in either medium, indicating complete growth inhibition at this level.

4.2.3 Inhibitory Effect of Combined Lactic and Acetic Acid

Table 6 shows the growth inhibition of *B. subtilis* (Bs1 and Bs2) and *B. licheniformis* (Bl1 and Bl2) under varying concentrations of combined lactic and acetic acid and their corresponding pH values. Growth was assessed in both BHI broth and BHI agar media.

Table 66: Growth Inhibition of Bacillus Strains with combined Lactic and Acetic Acid

pH	Concentration	<i>B. subtilis</i>				<i>B. licheniformis</i>			
		Bs1 broth	Bs1 agar	Bs2 broth	Bs2 agar	Bl1 broth	Bl1 agar	Bl2 broth	Bl2 agar
5.86	20.6 mM	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++
5.24	42.05mM	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4.83	63.5 mM	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4.58	84.95 mM	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4.38	106 mM	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

This table demonstrates the growth or inhibition of *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis* under varying concentrations of lactic acid. Symbol explanation: Symbols: +++ (strong growth), - (no growth).

When acetic acid and lactic acid were combined, the results demonstrated significant antimicrobial potential. As shown in Table 6, at a concentration of 20.6 mM and a corresponding pH of 5.86, strong growth (+++) was observed for all strains in both BHI broth and agar media. At a concentration of 42.05 mM and pH 5.24, no growth (-) was recorded for any strain in either medium. Similarly, at concentrations of 63.5 mM or higher, complete growth inhibition (-) was consistently observed for all strains across both BHI broth and agar media.

4.2.4 Impact of Undissociated Acid Concentration on Bacterial Growth

To evaluate the role of pH and acid concentration on growth inhibition of *B. subtilis* (Bs1 and Bs2) and *B. licheniformis* (Bl1 and B2), the concentrations of undissociated lactic and acetic acids were calculated using the Henderson-Hasselbalch equation. The pKa values used for these calculations were 3.86 for lactic acid and 4.76 for acetic acid. The calculated concentrations of undissociated acid are presented in appendix 3.

The effect of pH and total lactic acid concentration on undissociated acid concentration and bacterial growth was evaluated. At pH 5.65 and a total lactic acid concentration of 42.05 mM, the undissociated lactic acid concentration was calculated to be 0.67 mM. Under these conditions, growth was observed for both *B. subtilis* (Bs1, Bs2) and *B. licheniformis* (Bl1, Bl2) in both BHI broth and agar media (Table 4). At pH 4.80 and a total lactic acid concentration of 63.5 mM, the undissociated acid concentration increased to 6.53 mM, and no growth (-) was observed for all strains in either medium.

For acetic acid, growth inhibition was observed at lower concentrations and higher pH compared to lactic acid. At pH 5.41 and a total concentration of 42.05 mM, the concentration of undissociated acid was calculated to be 7.69 mM, which was sufficient to inhibit the growth of all bacterial strains in BHI broth while very weak growth in agar media for some strains (Table 5). At pH 4.85 and a total concentration of 63.5 mM, the concentration of undissociated acetic acid increased to 28.47 mM, where no growth was observed. These results suggest that acetic acid is more effective than lactic acid at lower concentrations.

4.3 Antimicrobial effect of Lactic acid bacteria

4.3.1 Optical Density and Growth Inhibition

The effect of supernatants from *L. lactis* and *L. fermentum* on the growth of *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis* was analyzed by measuring optical density (OD) before and after 24 hours of incubation. Table 7 shows the OD values and corresponding pH changes for each strain under different mixing ratios (70:30, 60:40, 50:50, and 25:25:50).

Table 7: Average OD-values and pH changes before and after 24 hours for *Bacillus* strains under different mixture ratios

Mixture Ratio	Strain	OD Before	pH Before	OD After	pH after
70:30 70% supernatant and 30% <i>Bacillus</i> media	<i>B. subtilis</i> + <i>L. fermentum</i>	0.04	4.45	0.05	4.48
	<i>B. licheniformis</i> + <i>L. fermentum</i>	0.11	4.44	0.12	4.45
	<i>B. subtilis</i> + <i>L. lactis</i>	0.06	5.28	0.07	5.40
	<i>B. licheniformis</i> + <i>L. lactis</i>	0.10	5.16	0.08	5.21
60:40 60% supernatant and 40% <i>Bacillus</i> media	<i>B. subtilis</i> + <i>L. fermentum</i>	0.06	4.61	0.03	4.65
	<i>B. licheniformis</i> + <i>L. fermentum</i>	0.11	4.55	0.04	4.62
	<i>B. subtilis</i> + <i>L. lactis</i>	0.07	5.52	0.08	5.97
	<i>B. licheniformis</i> + <i>L. lactis</i>	0.12	5.32	0.05	5.52
50:50 50% supernatant and 50% <i>Bacillus</i> media	<i>B. subtilis</i> + <i>L. fermentum</i>	0.05	4.73	0.05	4.74
	<i>B. licheniformis</i> + <i>L. fermentum</i>	0.12	4.64	0.04	4.67
	<i>B. subtilis</i> + <i>L. lactis</i>	0.07	5.78	0.063	6.08
	<i>B. licheniformis</i> + <i>L. lactis</i>	0.11	5.62	0.05	5.69
25:25:50 25% supernatant, 25% Milli-Q water, 50% <i>Ba-</i> <i>cillus</i> media	<i>B. subtilis</i> + <i>L. fermentum</i> + Milli Q	0.05	4.94	0.04	4.97
	<i>B. licheniformis</i> + <i>L. fermentum</i> + Milli Q	0.14	4.87	0.12	4.84
	<i>B. subtilis</i> + <i>L. lactis</i> + Milli Q	0.05	6.02	0.06	5.95
	<i>B. licheniformis</i> + <i>L. lactis</i> + Milli Q	0.13	5.74	0.06	5.95

The table presents the optical density (OD) values and pH changes observed for *Bacillus* strains (*B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis*) before and after 24 hours of incubation with supernatants from *L. lactis* and *L. fermentum*. Four mixture ratios were tested: 70:30, 60:40, 50:50, and 25:25:50. The results demonstrate that supernatants from *L. fermentum* have stronger inhibitory effects on *Bacillus* strains than those from *L. lactis*, as reflected in the reduced OD values and more pronounced pH changes. Significant differences in growth inhibition and pH reduction were observed across the tested conditions, particularly for combinations involving *B. subtilis* with *L. fermentum*, *B. licheniformis* with *L. fermentum*, *B. subtilis* with *L. lactis*, and *B. licheniformis* with *L. lactis*.

As shown in Table 7, the results reveal clear differences in growth inhibition depending on the type of supernatant and the applied mixing ratios. A paired t-test showed a statistically significant reduction in OD after incubation ($p=0.0077$), confirming the inhibitory effect of the supernatants on the growth of *Bacillus* strains. These findings demonstrate that supernatants affect bacterial growth and contribute to growth inhibition.

Under the 70:30 mixing ratio, *B. subtilis* combined with *L. fermentum* increased in OD from 0.04 to 0.05, while *B. licheniformis* with *L. fermentum* showed a slight increase from 0.11 to 0.12. In comparison, *B. subtilis* with *L. lactis* increased in OD from 0.06 to 0.07, whereas *B. licheniformis* with *L. lactis* showed a decrease from 0.10 to 0.08. However, *B. subtilis* appeared to be more sensitive to this inhibition, as confirmed by lower visible growth when plated on BHI-agar. The results of the agar plate growth are presented in Appendix 4.

The 60:40 mixture ratio led to a pronounced reduction in OD for *B. subtilis* with *L. fermentum* (0.06 to 0.03), and *B. licheniformis* with *L. fermentum* showed a reduction from 0.11 to 0.04. Meanwhile, *B. subtilis* with *L. lactis* exhibited a minor increase in OD from 0.07 to 0.08, while *B. licheniformis* with *L. lactis* showed a substantial reduction from 0.12 to 0.05.

A slight reduction in OD was observed under the 50:50 mixture ratio for *B. subtilis* with *L. fermentum* (0.048 to 0.046), while *B. licheniformis* with *L. fermentum* exhibited a larger reduction from 0.12 to 0.04. Similarly, *B. subtilis* with *L. lactis* decreased in OD from 0.07 to 0.06, and *B. licheniformis* with *L. lactis* dropped from 0.11 to 0.05.

In the 25:25:50 mixture ratio, *B. subtilis* with *L. fermentum* showed a reduction in OD from 0.05 to 0.04, while *B. licheniformis* with *L. fermentum* decreased from 0.14 to 0.12. The OD for *B. subtilis* with *L. lactis* increased slightly from 0.05 to 0.06, whereas *B. licheniformis* with *L. lactis* decreased markedly from 0.13 to 0.06.

4.3.2 pH Analysis of *Bacillus* Strains with Lactic acid bacteria supernatants at varying ratio

As shown in figure 2, the results highlight the differences in pH changes before and after 24 hours of incubation for *Bacillus* strains exposed to supernatants from *L. lactis* and *L. fermentum* under different mixing ratios.

Figure 2: pH Values Before and After 24-Hour Incubation for *Bacillus* Strains at Different Mixture Ratios

The plot shows pH changes before and after 24 hours of incubation for *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis* strains exposed to *L. fermentum* and *L. lactis* at mixing ratios of 25:25:50, 50:50, 60:40, and 70:30. The grey bars represent pH before incubation, while black bars represent pH after incubation. Each subplot corresponds to a specific *Bacillus* strain paired with either *L. fermentum* or *L. Lactis*, highlighting differences in pH due to acidification by the supernatants.

The results show that supernatants from *L. fermentum* consistently resulted in lower pH values (<5) compared to those from *L. lactis* (≥ 5). For example, at a 50:50 mixing ratio, the pH for *B. subtilis* with *L. fermentum* increased from 4.73 to 4.74, while *B. subtilis* with *L. lactis* increased from 5.78 to 6.08. Similarly, at the 25:25:50 mixing ratio, *B. licheniformis* with *L. fermentum* showed a pH decrease from 4.87 to 4.84, whereas *B. licheniformis* with *L. lactis* showed an increase from 5.74 to 5.95.

These results show that *L. fermentum* supernatants create a more acidic environment, which inhibit bacterial growth more effectively compared to *L. lactis*. The data is presented in Table 7 for further reference.

These observations highlight the differing impacts of *L. lactis* and *L. fermentum* supernatants on the incubation environment's pH values. To further evaluate the consistency and variability of pH changes across the different mixture ratios, the standard deviations of pH measurements were calculated separately for each lactic acid bacterium strain. These values provide insight into the reliability of the experimental conditions and are presented in Table 8 and Table 9.

Table 8: Standard Deviation for *L. fermentum* pH Measurements Across Different Mixture Ratios

Mixture Ratio	SD (pH Before)	SD (pH After)
25:25:50	0.10	0.09
50:50	0.06	0.10
60:40	0.04	0.02
70:30	0.01	0.02

The table presents the standard deviation of pH measurements for *L. fermentum* across various mixture ratios. The standard deviations were calculated to assess the variability in pH data recorded at the start and after 24 hours of incubation.

Table 9: Standard Deviation for *L. lactis* pH Measurements Across Different Mixture Ratios

Mixture Ratio	SD (pH Before)	SD (pH After)
25:25:50	0.20	0.00
50:50	0.11	0.28
60:40	0.14	0.32
70:30	0.09	0.13

The table presents the standard deviation of pH measurements for *L. lactis* across various mixture ratios. The standard deviations were calculated to assess the variability in pH data recorded at the start and after 24 hours of incubation.

The standard deviations for *L. fermentum* pH measurements are presented in table 8. Before incubation, the standard deviations ranged from 0.01 at the 70:30 ratio to 0.06 at the 50:50 ratio. After incubation, the standard deviations ranged from 0.02 to 0.10. In comparison, the standard deviations for *L. lactis* pH measurements, shown in table 9, ranged from 0.09 at the 70:30 ratio to 0.20 at the 25:25:50 ratio. After incubation, the standard deviations ranged from 0 at the 25:25:50 ratio to 0.32 at the 60:40 mixture.

4.3.3 Organic acids quantification

To quantify the concentration of lactic acid and acetic acid in the samples, standard curves were first made using known concentrations of these acids. By plotting these concentrations on a linear graph, calibration equations were derived. These equations allowed for the determination of the precise

concentrations of lactic acid and acetic acid in the samples based on the HPLC measurements. The standard curves used for this analysis are presented in appendix 6.

The results demonstrate variations in acetic acid and lactic acid concentrations across the different mixing ratios and bacterial isolates. The findings are summarized below, with visual representations provided in figures 3-6 and detailed numerical data available in Appendix 5.

- **Lactic Acid Concentrations**

Based on the results presented in figures 3 and 4, HPLC analysis demonstrated that *L. fermentum* produces significantly higher concentrations of lactic acid compared to *L. lactis* across all mixing ratios.

For samples treated with *L. lactis*, lactic acid concentrations ranged from 0.189 mg/mL to 0.961 mg/mL, with the highest concentration observed at the 70:30 mixing ratio. *B. licheniformis* (Green-labeled bars) showed slightly higher concentrations than *B. subtilis* (blue-labeled bars) across most mixing ratios.

Figure 2: Lactic Acid Levels in *Bacillus* Strains Treated with *L. lactis*

Figure 3 depicts the lactic acid concentrations (mg/mL) in *B. subtilis* (blue) and *B. licheniformis* (green) samples treated with *L. lactis* supernatant at mixing ratios of 25:25:50, 50:50, 60:40, and 70:30. Measurements were taken at two time points: the start (0–30 minutes post-mixing) and the end (20–24 hours post-mixing). The results indicate higher lactic acid production at higher proportions of supernatant (70:30), with *B. licheniformis* consistently producing slightly higher concentrations than *B. subtilis*.

Samples treated with *L. fermentum* exhibited lactic acid concentrations ranging from 0.355 mg/mL to 1.009 mg/mL, which are significantly higher than those of *L. lactis*. This shows that *L. lactis*, has a higher concentration at mixing ratios with greater proportions of supernatant (70:30).

Figure 3: Lactic Acid Concentrations in *Bacillus* Strains Treated with *L. fermentum* Supernatant

The bar graph depicts the concentration of lactic acid (mg/mL) in samples of *B. subtilis* (blue) and *B. licheniformis* (green) treated with *L. fermentum* supernatant across mixing ratios (25:25:50, 50:50, 60:40, and 70:30). Measurements were taken at the start (0–30 minutes post-mixing) and end (20–24 hours post-mixing) time points.

- **Acetic Acid Concentrations**

HPLC results also revealed differences in acetic acid production between *L. lactis* and *L. fermentum*, as illustrated in Figures 5 and 6. For samples treated with *L. lactis* (Figure 5), acetic acid concentrations ranged from 0.057 mg/mL to 0.072 mg/mL. The highest concentration (0.072) was observed at the 70:30 mixing ratio, while the lowest (0.057 mg/mL) was recorded at the 25:25:50 mixing ratio.

Figure 4: Acetic Acid Concentrations in *Bacillus* Strains Treated with *L. lactis* Supernatant

The bar graph displays the concentration of acetic acid (mg/mL) in samples of *B. subtilis* (blue) and *B. licheniformis* (green) treated with *L. lactis* supernatant at mixing ratios of 25:25:50, 50:50, 60:40, and 70:30. Measurements were taken at the start (0–30 minutes post-mixing) and the end (20–24 hours post-mixing) time points. Acetic acid concentrations remain relatively consistent across all mixing ratios, with values ranging from 0.056 mg/mL to 0.072 mg/mL at the start and 0.059 mg/mL to 0.071 mg/mL at the end. No significant differences between the strains or mixing ratios were observed.

In comparison, *L. fermentum* produced significantly higher concentrations of acetic acid, ranging from 0.115 mg/mL to 0.244 mg/mL, as shown in Figure 6. The highest concentration (0.244 mg/mL) was also observed at the 70:30 mixing ratio, emphasizing *L. fermentum*'s superior acidogenic capacity.

Figure 5: Acetic Acid Concentrations in Bacillus Strains Treated with *L. fermentum* Supernatant

The bar graph shows the concentration of acetic acid (mg/mL) in samples containing *B. subtilis* (blue) and *B. licheniformis* (green) exposed to *L. fermentum*'s supernatant under different mixing ratios ((25:25:50, 50:50, 60:40, and 70:30) at start (0-30 min. after mixing) and end time (20-24 hours after mixing) points. The results show that acetic acid concentrations increase with higher supernatant proportions, particularly after 20-24 hours. This indicates that the inhibitory potential of *L. fermentum*'s supernatant is proportional to its concentration in the mixture. Both bacterial strains exhibited similar trends, though slight variations between *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis* suggest differences in their susceptibility to acetic acid.

To sum it up, *L. fermentum* produced an average of 0.181 mg/mL acetic acid, which is 63.4% higher compared to *L. lactis*, with an average of 0.066 mg/mL. The average lactic acid concentration was 0.702 mg/mL for *L. fermentum* and 0.349 mg/mL for *L. lactis*, corresponding to a 50.28% higher concentration in *L. fermentum*.

4.4 Discussion

This study highlights the importance of controlling the growth of *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis* to improve shelf life and reduce microbial spoilage in plant-based foods. The experiment has shown that acetic acid exhibits significantly higher antimicrobial activity compared to lactic acid, particularly at moderately acidic pH values. Furthermore, *L. fermentum* was found to have a stronger inhibitory effect on *Bacillus* spp. compared to *L. lactis*. These results are critical for developing strategies to enhance the microbial safety and quality of plant-based products.

4.4.1 Effectiveness of Organic Acids

The study confirmed the critical role of pH and organic acid concentration in inhibiting *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis*. Acetic acid demonstrated superior antimicrobial effects, which can be attributed to its ability to remain partially undissociated at moderately acidic pH values. This allows it to penetrate bacterial membranes and disrupt intracellular processes. This mechanism contrasts with HCl, which primarily inhibits growth by lowering environmental pH without direct molecular interactions with bacterial cells.

Importantly, acetic acid exhibited significant inhibitory effects even at higher pH value (5.65–4.85), requiring lower concentrations to achieve these effects. In comparison, lactic acid was less effective under similar conditions, requiring both a lower pH and higher concentrations to produce comparable results. These findings align with prior research by Hsiao & Siebert (1999), who emphasized the enhanced permeability and metabolic interference caused by acetic acid. These findings are also consistent with those of Reis et al. (2012), who also found that acetic acid demonstrated higher antimicrobial activity than lactic acid. However, the observed resilience of *Bacillus* spp. on agar media differs from previous studies, which may be attributed to differences in experimental setups.

The difference in effectiveness can be attributed to the pKa values of the two acids, which determine how much of the acid is in its undissociated form at different pH values. Acetic acid with a pKa of 4.76, maintains a higher concentration of undissociated acid at higher pH values compared to lactic acid, which has a pKa of 3.86. For example, at pH 5.41 a total acetic acid concentration of 42.05mM resulted in 7.69 mM undissociated, enough to completely inhibit *Bacillus* growth in BHI broth and only very weak growth in agar media. In comparison, at pH 5.65 and concentration at 42.05mM lactic acid produced only 0.67 mM undissociated acid, where *Bacillus* strains could still grow. Only at lower pH values (4.80) and higher total concentrations did lactic acid reach an undissociated concentration (6.53mM) sufficient to fully inhibit bacterial growth. The significantly higher proportion of undissociated acetic acid at pH 5.41 compared to lactic acid at pH 5.65 underscores because acetic acid is more effective at higher pH levels and lower total concentrations.

The synergistic effect observed when combining acetic acid and lactic acid in this study aligns with findings from previous research, which highlight that such combinations can enhance antimicrobial efficacy. This is evident in complete growth inhibition of *Bacillus* strains at lower concentrations of combined acids (42mM at pH 5.24) compared to their individual effects. The combined acids create a more unfavorable environment.

Interestingly, a discrepancy was observed between bacterial growth in liquid BHI broth and solid agar media. At lower pH values (≤ 3.5), no visible growth was detected in both BHI broth and agar media, yet colonies appeared on agar plates after 20-24 hours incubation. This highlights the resilience of *Bacillus* strains, which can endure unfavorable conditions in liquid media and recover under more favorable environments. One plausible explanation is that *B. subtilis* and *B. Licheniformis*' ability to thrive in aerobic environments. Solid media facilitate improved oxygen diffusion, which supports their energy metabolisms and activates survival mechanisms to adapt to acid stress. Additionally, solid media may buffer local pH conditions around colonies, reducing the uniform acid stress observed in liquid media. This combination of oxygen availability and pH buffering makes solid media particularly favorable for many aerobic or facultative aerobic bacteria, such as *Bacillus* spp.

4.4.2 Application of Lactic Acid Bacteria

L. fermentum exhibited a stronger inhibitory effect on *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis* compared to *L. lactis*. This is likely due to its production of both lactic acid and acetic acid, as confirmed by HPLC-analysis. The results revealed that *L. fermentum* produced an average acetic acid concentration of 0.181 mg/mL, which is 63.4% more compared to *L. lactis* (0.066 mg/mL). Additionally, the average lactic acid concentration for *L. fermentum* was 0.702 mg/mL, which is 50.3% higher *L. lactis* (0.349 mg/mL). This increased production of acids contributes to a lower pH, creating a more hostile environment for *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis*.

Moreover, the production of bacteriocins by *L. fermentum* may have further contributed to the observed inhibition. Specific bacteriocins, such as Fermencin SA715, Fermencin SD11, and Bacteriocin L23, have been shown to be effective against Gram-positive bacteria, including *Bacillus* spp. These bacteriocins are known for their stability across a wide range of pH values and temperatures, as well as their ability to disrupt bacterial membranes and induce cell lysis (Fernandes & Jobby, 2022). While this aspect was not directly tested in the current experiment, it highlights the potential of *L. fermentum* as a bio preservative.

These differences in organic acids (and theoretically bacteriocin) correlate with the OD values observed in Table 7. For instance, at a 70:30 mixture ratio, the OD of *L. fermentum* + *B. subtilis* increased slightly from 0.04 to 0.05, indicating minimal bacterial growth. In contrast, for *L. lactis* + *B. subtilis* under the same conditions, the OD increased more substantially from 0.06 to 0.07, indicating weaker inhibition. These results underline the importance of selecting appropriate bacterial cultures based on the desired application and the specific microbial target.

4.4.3 Importance of pH

The results underscore the critical role of pH in inhibiting *Bacillus* spp. growth of both *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis* was inhibited at $\text{pH} \leq 4.5$, emphasizing the importance of acid control in plant-based foods. Measurements (Figure 2) revealed that *L. fermentum* supernatants produced significantly lower pH values compared to those from *L. lactis*, aligning with the observed stronger inhibitory potential of *L. fermentum*.

However, the resilience of *Bacillus* spp. on solid media at low pH values highlights their ability to survive harsh conditions in liquid environments and recover when conditions improved. This suggests that pH reduction alone may not suffice to fully inhibit *Bacillus* spp. growth in all contexts. A combination of acidification with other preservation technologies, such as bacteriocins, aseptic packaging, or thermal treatments, may be necessary to ensure comprehensive microbial control.

4.4.4 Limitation and Future studies

One limitation of this study is the difference between laboratory conditions and real food environments. Laboratory media, such as BHI broth and agar, do not fully replicate the complexities of real food matrices, where factors such as water activity, nutrient composition, and competing microbial populations can influence the efficacy of preservation methods. Future studies should include experiments in real food products, such as plant-based meat substitutes or dairy alternatives, to validate the robustness of the proposed methods.

Additionally, the role of bacteriocins produced by *L. fermentum*, such as Fermencin SA715, and Bacteriocin L23; in inhibiting *Bacillus* spp. warrants further investigation (Fernandes & Jobby, 2022). Exploring the stability of these bacteriocins under various environmental conditions (e.g., pH, temperature) could provide valuable insights for their application in food preservation. Combining acidification with natural antimicrobial compounds or novel preservation strategies could enhance the overall effectiveness of microbial inhibition in plant-based products (Yu et al., 2023).

5 Conclusion

The aim of this thesis was to investigate methods to inhibit *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis* in plant-based foods using organic acids and LAB. By focusing on the effects of pH, organic acid concentrations, and LAB supernatants, the study identified effective strategies to mitigate spoilage and enhance food safety.

Acetic acid demonstrated superior antimicrobial activity compared to lactic acid primarily due to its higher pKa of 4.76. The higher pKa allows acetic acid to retain a greater proportion of its undissociated form at elevated pH values, enabling it to penetrate bacterial cells and disrupt intracellular processes. Acetic acid effectively inhibited bacterial growth at lower concentrations (>42.05 mM) and higher pH values (≤ 5.41), with the undissociated concentration of acetic acid calculated to be 7.69 mM. These conditions resulted in the complete absence of growth in broth and minimal growth on agar plates. In contrast, lactic acid with a lower pKa of 3.86, required higher concentrations (≥ 63.5 mM) and lower pH levels (≤ 4.80) to achieve effective inhibition. Under these conditions, the undissociated lactic acid concentration was calculated to be 6.53 mM, which was sufficient to fully inhibit bacterial growth. The combination of acetic acid and lactic acid exhibited a synergistic effect, significantly enhancing antibacterial efficacy. This synergy allowed for complete inhibition at lower concentrations than when the acids were used individually. At a combined concentration of 42.5 mM, no bacterial growth was detected in either broth or agar media. HCl also showed inhibition of *Bacillus* growth at $\text{pH} \leq 3.5$, with no growth observed in broth media and limited recovery on agar plates. However, the dissociated ionic form of HCl limited its efficacy by preventing penetration of bacterial membranes, making it less effective under neutral to acidic conditions.

Among the LAB strains studied, *L. fermentum* was the most effective due to its higher production of both lactic acid and acetic acid (Supernatants from *L. fermentum* demonstrated stronger antimicrobial effects on *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis* compared to *L. lactis*, attributed to its higher production of acetic acid (0.181 mg/mL, 63.4% more) and lactic acid (0.355–1.009 mg/mL vs. 0.189–0.961 mg/mL for *L. lactis*). This acid production created a more unfavorable environment, resulting in greater inhibition, as reflected in lower OD values after 24 hours. This strain created an environment highly unfavorable for *Bacillus* growth and demonstrated a strong ability to lower pH, further enhancing its antimicrobial effects. These findings underscore the importance of selecting LAB strains based on their specific metabolic and antimicrobial properties to develop tailored solutions for different food applications.

In conclusion, this research demonstrates the potential of using organic acids and LAB as natural effective methods to control *Bacillus* spp. in plant-based foods. These findings provide a foundation for developing scalable, sustainable strategies to improve food safety, extend shelf-life, and meet consumer demands for clean-label products.

6 Future Perspectives

This bachelor thesis has explored the potential of inhibiting *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis* by using acids (HCL, acetic acid, lactic acid) and LAB. The results validate that combining organic acids, particularly acetic and lactic acid, effectively suppresses bacterial growth and underscores their relevance as natural and sustainable food preservation agents. By utilizing simple and controlled experimental setups, this study provides a strong methodological foundation for future research while acknowledging the need to address limitations such as scalability and real-world application.

The critical strengths of the methods employed in this research is their direct applicability to current food preservation challenges. However, the controlled laboratory conditions differ from the complexity of commercial food systems. For example, variations in pH, temperature, and water activity in real-world food matrices may alter the efficacy of organic acids and LAB-derived antimicrobials. Future research should, therefore, prioritize evaluating these methods in more complex food systems, including plant-based products such as fermented beverages, dairy alternatives, and meat substitutes. Investigating these under realistic storage conditions would provide a comprehensive understanding of their performance and limitations.

In addition to the organic acids investigated, LAB also produce antimicrobial peptides known as bacteriocins, which represent an exciting opportunity for advancing preservation strategies. Bacteriocins, such as nisin and pediocin, have shown potent inhibitory effects against spoilage and pathogenic microorganisms. Their combination with organic acids could create synergistic effects, enhancing antimicrobial efficacy. Evaluating their behavior in diverse food matrices and developing advanced delivery systems, such as encapsulation or active packaging, could ensure stability and controlled release, making them viable for industrial-scale applications.

The significance of this study lies not only in its contribution to food safety but also in its alignment with global sustainability goals. By reducing reliance on synthetic preservatives and extending shelf life, these methods can help mitigate food waste while catering to growing consumer demand for clean-label and minimally processed products. Furthermore, the environmental and economic benefits of adopting natural preservation methods highlight their importance in addressing broader food security challenges. These findings pave the way for integrating innovative and sustainable food preservation strategies into modern food systems, addressing both current challenges and future demands for a resilient global food industry.

7 Literature

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8 Appendix

Appendix 1 - Preparation of Acid Solutions

The preparation of lactic acid and acetic acid solutions followed the same calculation method, with adjustments for their respective molar masses. For lactic acid, the molar mass (90.08 g/mol) was divided by 2, resulting in a base concentration of 45 g per 500 mL. Similarly, for acetic acid, the molar mass (60.06 g/mol) was divided by 2, resulting in a base concentration of 30 g per 500 mL. These base solutions were used to prepare five specific concentrations for each acid.

From these base solutions, the following volumes were calculated to achieve the desired concentrations:

Concentration (mM)	Equation	Equation number
106.4	$\frac{0.106M \cdot 500mL}{1M} = 53mL.$ <p>53 mL of the stock solution was used for both lactic acid and acetic acid</p>	Eq1
84.95	$\frac{0.08495M \cdot 500mL}{1M} = 42.4mL$ <p>42.5 mL of the stock solution was used for both lactic acid and acetic acid.</p>	Eq2
63.5	$\frac{0.0635M \cdot 500mL}{1M} = 31.8mL$ <p>31.8 mL of the stock solution was used for both lactic acid and acetic acid.</p>	Eq3
42.05	$\frac{0.04205M \cdot 500mL}{1M} = 21.03mL$ <p>21.8 mL of the stock solution was used for both lactic acid and acetic acid.</p>	Eq4
0.6 mM	$\frac{0.0206M \cdot 500mL}{1M} = 10.3mL$ <p>10.3mL of the stock solution was used for both lactic acid and acetic acid.</p>	Eq5
Combined acid solution	<p>To investigate the combined effect of lactic acid and acetic acid, solutions were prepared by mixing equal volumes (5 mL each) of lactic acid and acetic acid stock solutions at the same concentration. This resulted in a final volume of 10 mL for</p>	

	<p>each mixture, ensuring that the final concentration of the combined solution matched the concentration of the individual acids.</p> <p>For example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 106.4 mM mixture: 5 mL of 106.4 mM lactic acid solution + 5 mL of 106.4 mM acetic acid solution = 10 mL total volume. • Similarly, mixtures were prepared for concentrations of 84.95 mM, 63.5 mM, 42.05 mM, and 20.6 mM 	
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Appendix 2 - Pictures of acid effect

Table 1 10: Visual Growth Indicators for Bacillus Strains in Broth and Agar Media

Growth Indicator	Broth media	Agar plate
+++ (Strong growth)		
++ (moderate growth)		
+ (weak growth)		
+/- (very weak growth)		
- (no growth)		

Appendix 3 - Effect of pH on Undissociated Acid Concentrations and Bacterial Growth

To evaluate the relationship between pH and the concentrations of undissociated lactic and acetic acids, the Henderson-Hasselbalch equation was utilized:

$$pH = pKa + \log\left(\frac{[A^-]}{[HA]}\right) \text{ (Eq. 1)}$$

Where:

$[A^-]$ = Concentration of dissociated acid

$[HA]$ = Concentration of undissociated acid

pKa = Acid dissociation constant

By changing the equation, the concentration of the undissociated acid $[HA]$ was calculated as follows:

$$[HA] = \frac{[Total\ Acid]}{1 + 10^{pH - pKa}} \text{ (Eq.2)}$$

The pKa values used for the calculations were 3.86 for lactic acid and 4.76 for acetic acid, based on their known dissociation constants. Tables 3a and 3b summarize the calculated concentrations of undissociated acids at different pH levels and total acid concentrations.

Table 1a: Calculated Concentrations of Undissociated Lactic Acid at Different pH Levels and Total Acid Concentrations

pH	Concentration	pKa	Undissociated (mM)
6.78	20.6 mM	3.86	0.02
5.65	42.05mM	3.86	0.67
4.80	63.5 mM	3.86	6.53
4.36	84.95 mM	3.86	20.40
4.06	106 mM	3.86	41.00

Table 1b: Calculated Concentrations of Undissociated Acetic Acid at Different pH Levels and Total Acid Concentrations

pH	Concentration	pKa	Undissociated (mM)
6.56	20.6 mM	4.76	0.32
5.41	42.05mM	4.76	7.69
4.85	63.5 mM	4.76	28.47
4.67	84.95 mM	4.76	46.86
4.51	106 mM	4.76	67.84

Appendix 4- Pictures of BHI-agar from mixtures

Table 1: Mixture 50% supernatant (*L.fermentum* or *L.lactis*) and 50% Bacillus (*B.subtilis* or *B.licheniformis*) grown on plates shown both from start to end (overnight 18-24 hours).

Mixture 50/50	Start	End
<i>B.subtilis</i> + <i>L.lactis</i>		
<i>B.Licheniformis</i> + <i>L.lactis</i>		
<i>B.subtilis</i> + <i>L.Fermentum</i>		

<i>B.licheniformis</i> + <i>L.Fermentum</i>		

Table 2: Mixture 60% supernatant (*L.fermentum* or *L.lactis*) and 40% Bacillus (*B.subtilis* or *B.licheniformis*) grown on plates shown both from start to end (overnight 18-24 hours).

Mixture 60%/40%	start	end
<i>B.subtilis</i> + <i>L.lactis</i>		

<p><i>B.Licheniformis</i> + <i>L.lactis</i></p>		
<p><i>B.subtilis</i> + <i>L.Fermentum</i></p>		
<p><i>B.licheniformis</i> + <i>L.Fermentum</i></p>		

Table 3: Mixture 50% supernatant (*L.fermentum* or *L.lactis*), 25% Bacillus (*B.subtilis* or *B.licheniformis*) and 25% milli-q water grown on plates shown both from start to end (overnight 18-24 hours).

Mixture 50%/25%/25%	Start	End
<i>B.subtilis</i> + <i>L.lactis</i>		
<i>B.Licheniformis</i> + <i>L.lactis</i>		
<i>B.subtilis</i> + <i>L.Fermentum</i>		

Table 4: Mixture 70% supernatant (*L.fermentum* or *L.lactis*) and 30% Bacillus (*B.subtilis* or *B.licheniformis*) grown on plates shown both from start to end (overnight 18-24 hours).

Mixture 70%/30%	Start	end
<i>B.subtilis</i> + <i>L.lactis</i>		
<i>B.Licheniformis</i> + <i>L.lactis</i>		
<i>B.subtilis</i> + <i>L.Fermentum</i>		

Appendix 5 - pH Changes Before and After Incubation for *Bacillus* Strains Exposed to Supernatant Mixtures

Table 1:11 HPLC results showing the concentration of acetic acid present in the samples for both *L. lactis* and *L. fermentum*

L. lactis

	Mixing ratio	Concentration (mg/mL)
start	25:25:50	0.066
end	25:25:50	0.064
start	25:25:50	0.056
end	25:25:50	0.059
start	50:50	0.06
end	50:50	0.068
start	50:50	0.069
end	50:50	0.063
start	60:40	0.065
end	60:40	0.071
start	60:40	0.068
end	60:40	0.066
start	70:30	0.072
end	70:30	0.061
start	70:30	0.065
end	70:30	0.069

L. fermentum

	Mixing ratio	Concentration (mg/mL)
start	25:25:50	0.116
end	25:25:50	0.115
start	25:25:50	0.115
end	25:25:50	0.116
start	50:50	0.180
end	50:50	0.166
start	50:50	0.178
end	50:50	0.186
start	60:40	0.213
end	60:40	0.205
start	60:40	0.203
end	60:40	0.197
start	70:30	0.231
end	70:30	0.229
start	70:30	0.232
end	70:30	0.244

The tables show HPLC results of the concentration of acetic acid present in the samples for both *L. lactis* and *L. fermentum*. The blue color indicates samples with *B. subtilis*, isolated from dried faba beans, while the green color represents *B. licheniformis*, isolated from faba protein concentrate. The mixing ratios reflect the proportions used in the experiments: 70:30 (70% supernatant and 30% Bacillus media), 60:40 (60% supernatant and 40% Bacillus media), 50:50 (50% supernatant and 50% Bacillus media), and 25:25:50 (25% supernatant, 25% milli-Q water, and 50% Bacillus media). The table compares the variation in acetic acid concentrations across different experimental conditions, highlighting the differences between the two bacterial isolates and mixing ratios.

Table 2 12: HPLC results showing the concentration of lactic acid present in the samples for both *L. lactis* and *L. fermentum*

L. lactis

	Mixing ratio	Concentration (mg/mL)
start	25:25:50	0.189
end	25:25:50	0.218
start	25:25:50	0.24
end	25:25:50	0.201
start	50:50	0.258
end	50:50	0.295
start	50:50	0.255
end	50:50	0.312
start	60:40	0.355
end	60:40	0.311
start	60:40	0.374
end	60:40	0.345
start	70:30	0.347
end	70:30	0.447
start	70:30	0.475
end	70:30	0.961

L. fermentum

	Mixing ratio	Concentration (mg/mL)
start	25:25:50	0.355
end	25:25:50	0.361
start	25:25:50	0.436
end	25:25:50	0.405
start	50:50	0.604
end	50:50	0.671
start	50:50	0.729
end	50:50	0.701
start	60:40	0.818
end	60:40	0.852
start	60:40	0.773
end	60:40	0.819
start	70:30	0.907
end	70:30	0.880
start	70:30	1.009
end	70:30	0.919

The tables show HPLC results of the concentration of lactic acid present in the samples for both *L. lactis* and *L. fermentum*. The blue color indicates samples with *B. subtilis*, isolated from dried faba beans, while the green color represents *B. licheniformis*, isolated from faba protein concentrate. The mixing ratios reflect the proportions used in the experiments: 70:30 (70% supernatant and 30% Bacillus media), 60:40 (60% supernatant and 40% Bacillus media), 50:50 (50% supernatant and 50% Bacillus media), and 25:25:50 (25% supernatant, 25% milli-Q water, and 50% Bacillus media). The table compares the variation in lactic acid concentrations across different experimental conditions, highlighting the differences between the two bacterial isolates and mixing ratios.

Appendix 6: Standard curves for Lactic Acid for Acetic Acid Quantification

Figure 1: The standard curve for lactic acid (left) and acetic acid (right) were created using serial dilutions of lactic acid and acetic acid solutions to derive calibration equations. For lactic acid the linear equation $y = 159817x - 1144.7$ while acetic acid, the linear equation $y = 217825x - 5852.4$ was obtained. These calibration equations were used to quantify the concentrations of lactic acid and acetic acid in the samples based on their respective HPLC peak areas.